

Review Article

Toxicity Associated with Gold Nanoparticles: A Review

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Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are by far the most studied nanomaterials by the scientific fraternity, possibly due to their immense potential in medical applications. Nevertheless, there is a disparity of opinion that prevailed concerning the toxicity of AuNPs. This study, therefore, presents a systematic review concerning toxicity related to AuNPs with the help of recently published databases. The disparity is due to the fact that the adoption of various protocols in the assessment of toxicity over the years that led to divergent views about the actual safety of AuNPs. This paper has considered a few recent research works and their databases to assess the toxicity of AuNPs *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Further, this paper also discussed the possible approaches that could effectively minimize the lethal effects of AuNPs and elaborated on the future scope of this interesting and highly useful research. For time being, it is concluded here that nanomaterial safety data are scarce, and it is not even an exaggeration to say that that is even scarcer than reported.

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Introduction

Ever since the term nanotechnology was coined by Norio Taniguchi, a professor at Tokyo University, Japan in the year 1974, several prominent research and development (R&D) organizations, academic and non-academic institutions, and others have ventured their efforts across the globe to gain benefits out of this ever-growing field. The growth of nanomaterials and nano-products synthesized (engineered) using nanoscience and nanotechnology has been phenomenal and non-linear, as rightly predicted by Richard Feynman in his speech at the American Physical Society (1959) at Caltech that "There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom". Nanomaterials' widespread use and success can be attributed to their distinct qualities compared to their bulk counterparts, such as lightweight, low cost, small size, and more durability, to mention a few.

Other properties such as chemical (reactivity and reaction rates), electrical (conductivity), magnetic, optical (colour and transparency),

and physical (hardness and boiling point) have altered significantly as a result of nanoscience and nanotechnology and are now extremely valuable in the manufacture of high-end products. It may not be an exaggeration that there are no scientific, research, medical, aerodynamics, space, and other industrial fields that have not used nano-enabled products. For instance, engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) find potential applications in medicine, pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, energy production, environmental sciences, crop protection, transportation, housing, and electronics. Still, there is a considerable proliferation of ENMs and nanocomposites in the market, thanks to this ever-increasing field on a day-by-day basis. The nanoscience enabled nanomaterials/products were successfully used in the eradication of corona virus disease-2019 (COVID-19) [1].

Researchers, on the other hand, have proposed two schools of thought. One school believes there are no risks related to nanomaterials, while the other institution disagrees. Certain characteristics of anthropogenic origin nanomaterials, such as their size, mobility, and significant interaction with the host where they are deposited and dispersed, may make them dangerous. After recognizing this potential distinction, a few research groups have

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Figure 1: Most common gold nanoparticle assemblies and morphologies (After Freitas et al., 2018, Reference [11])

already initiated significant research under the name of “nanotoxicology research”. In order to adequately address nanotoxicology and its detrimental implications, if any, on humans, animals, the environment, and other living species, it is necessary to examine and understand recent technical advancements in the field of nanotechnology.

Nanomaterials found in the human environment may have the potential for toxicological effects. However, the current literature on the toxicological effects of nanomaterials is diverse. The current data are presented from studies without harmonization [2]. These studies have used different *in vitro* and *in vivo* test models, different sources of test nanomaterials, different methods for nanomaterial characterization, and different experimental conditions. Therefore,

Figure 2: Gold nanoparticles medical applications (After Gerber et al., 2013, Reference [13])

these data are hard to interpret. More research on nanomaterial characterization, biological interaction, bio distribution, toxicity, and health effects are needed. The test methods need to be validated. Positive and negative controls for nanotoxicity need to be identified. Toxicity data harmonization needs to be done. Therefore, general information is not currently available for risk evaluation of certain nanomaterials that might be present in consumer products or that may enter the market in the future. Standardized and validated methods are necessary for the toxicity assessment of nanomaterials. Therefore, in the absence of standardized validated methods, any specific regulatory testing requirements for nanomaterials are currently premature. The benefits of nanomaterials found currently in the human environment are many, but their overall adverse effects on human health are limited [3].

In recent years, various studies have been conducted to determine the potential toxicity of nanoparticles in response to significant concerns regarding nanotechnology’s safety. Nanomaterials’ distinctive qualities, such as their extremely small size, high reactivity, and unique tensile property, as well as their considerable magnetic properties, have sparked a great deal of interest in their use in biological, environmental, and industrial applications. As a result, concerns regarding the impact on the environment, human health, and safety have been raised. For example, there was a lot of debate about the toxicity of carbon nanotubes (CNTs), which are thought to induce tissue damage in animals [4]. On the other hand, various research investigations on the toxicity of CNTs have come up with conflicting results [5].

Unlike CNTs, the variety of AuNPs and their biomedical uses continues to grow daily. Biosensorics, bioimaging, photothermal treatment, targeted drug delivery, and mushroom growth are some of the applications of AuNPs. Therefore, human safety problems are becoming increasingly prominent. As a result, a deeper understanding of the potential toxicity hazards of current AuNPs and the resulting AuNPs has become critical. With the aforementioned considerations in mind, this research highlighted two crucial issues: a comprehensive recent review of AuNPs nanotoxicity, as well as feasible approaches to reduce or eliminate the lethal consequences of AuNPs toxicity.

Recent Studies of Gold Nanoparticles Toxicity: *In vivo* and *In vitro*

Numerous AuNPs shapes and topologies have been fabricated using various synthetic approaches. Nanospheres, nanoshells, nanorods, nanoclusters, nanocages, and nanostars are some of the diverse shapes of AuNPs [6-10]. The most common gold nanoparticle assemblages and morphologies are depicted in figure 1 [11]. AuNPs are widely utilized across the medical field due to their excellent biocompatibility, because of their high chemical and physical stability and ease to functionalize with biologically active organic molecules or atoms [12]. Various medical applications of AuNPs can be found in figure 2 [13]. AuNPs can directly conjugate and interact with diverse molecules containing proteins, drugs, antibodies, enzymes, nucleic acids and fluorescent dyes on their surfaces for diverse medical applications and biological activities [14-16].

Figure 3 shows how various molecules conjugate with AuNPs [10]. As previously indicated, there is a wide divergence of opinion among researchers on the toxicity of AuNPs. This paper initially, therefore, presents the literature survey of AuNPs toxicity, followed by summarizing a few studies associated with AuNPs toxicity (*in vivo* as well as *in vitro*) in table 1 and table 2, respectively.

Figure 3: (A) Biodistribution of AuNP in different organs at 2 hours post-injection. A Tukey's multiple comparisons test was done to compare the interactions between each AuNP size. (B) Comparison between the attenuation change in different organs derived from CT scans performed at 2 hours post-injection and biodistribution of AuNP in different organs at 2 hours post-injection (adapted from reference [49])

Biological Effects of AuNPs: A Comprehensive Viewpoint

As already stated in the introduction, as AuNPs have been widely used in various biomedical fields, human health may get affected through nanoparticle-protein interaction, immunogenicity, and cytotoxicity.

It was righteously articulated by Saptarshi *et al.* [37] that the interaction of nanoparticles with proteins is the basis of nanoparticle bio-reactivity, and this interaction gives rise to the formation of a dynamic nanoparticle-protein corona. The protein corona may influence cellular uptake, inflammation, accumulation,

degradation and clearance of the nanoparticles. The nanoparticle surface can induce conformational changes in adsorbed protein molecules, which may affect the overall bio-reactivity of the nanoparticle. In depth understanding of such interactions can be directed toward generating bio-compatible nanomaterials with controlled surface characteristics in a biological environment [37].

Gold nanoparticles synthesized using citrate and *Z. officinale* extract demonstrated very low protein adsorption, as reported by [38]. Both nanoparticles were non-platelet activating and non-complement activating on contact with whole human blood. They also did not aggregate other blood cells. However, nanoparticles synthesized with *Z. officinale* extract were highly stable at

Table 1: Recent studies of AuNPs *in vivo* toxicities

Organism	Possible Effects	Type of synthesis	References
Mice	High concentrated AuNPs induced decreases in body weight, red blood cells, and hematocrit.	Water-soluble gold nanoparticles	[17]
Mice	Alteration in cell shape, inhibition of proliferation, or mutation in DNA	Polyethylene glycol (PEG)-coated AuNPs	[18]
Swiss Mice	Trans-placental size-dependent clastogenic and epigenetic effects	Water-soluble gold nanoparticles	[19]
Rats	DNA damage in the cerebral cortex	Water-soluble gold nanoparticles	[20]
Sprague-Dawley rats	No threats were found	Water-soluble gold nanoparticles	[21]
Wistar Rats	Potentially safe (no cardio toxic effects, echocardiography, arterial pressure, biochemical and histopathological analyses were found)	Biodegradable lipid-core nanocapsules	[22]
Albino rats	Histological changes in the lung tissue	Water-soluble gold nanoparticles	[23]
Rats	Mild changes in kidney, liver and testis	Biological and Fusarium oxysporum	[24]
Rats	Lung retention was found	Bio-persistent gold nanoparticles	[25]
Male albino rats	Ultra-small AuNPs showed low or no toxicity	Green synthesized ultra-small gold nanoparticles (Egyptian propolis extract)	[26]

Table 2: Recent and significant studies of AuNPs *in vitro* toxicities

Organism	Possible Effects	Type of synthesis	References
Cervix carcinoma epithelial cells (HeLa)	Necrosis	Water-soluble gold nanoparticles	[27]
Small airway epithelial cells (SAECs)	Oxidative stress-related cytotoxicity and genotoxicity in SAECs	Water-soluble gold nanoparticles	[28]
Human primary lymphocytes and murine macrophages	Proliferative activity, mitotic, apoptotic, necrotic markers, chromosomal damage	Spherical citrate-capped Au NPs	[29]
Bronchial epithelial cell line BEAS-2B, Human embryonic kidney cell line	Chinese hamster ovary cell line CHO damage	Citrate stabilized gold nanoparticles	[30]
Somatic and tumor cells	No significant cytotoxic effects found	Chitosan based gold nanoparticles	[31]
Chinese hamster ovary cells	No genotoxic effects found	Citrate-stabilized gold nanoparticles	[32]
Heart, kidney and lung	Larger sizes (42.5 and 61.2 nm) and smaller size (6.2 and 24.3 nm) AUNPs induced oxidative stress	Water soluble AuNPs	[33]
Human Cancer Cells	Toxic threat found	Biomimetic gold nanoparticles	[34]
Cholesterol molar ratio, Span 60: Tween 60 M ratio	Showed dose-dependent cytotoxicity and significant up-regulation of mRNA expression	Green synthesis AuNPs	[35]
Gastric buffer	Showed lesser toxicity	Cabotegravir - biodegradable gold nanoparticles	[36]

physiological conditions compared to citrate capped nanoparticles, which aggregated.

Ajdari et al. [39] investigated AuNPs interactions in blood using thromboelastography as a rapid screening tool to monitor their influence on blood coagulation. The 1.2 nM colloidal AuNPs ranging from 12 to 85 nm do not affect the blood. However, 5 nM AuNPs demonstrate pro-thrombogenic concentration-dependent effects with a reduction in clot formation.

To better understand the interaction of AuNPs with common human blood proteins, [40] performed absorbance, fluorescence quenching, circular dichroism, dynamic light scattering, and electron microscopy measurements on surface-functionalized water-soluble AuNPs having a diameter range from 5 to 100 nm in the presence of common human blood proteins: albumin, fibrinogen, α -globulin, histone, and insulin. It was found that the gold NPs strongly associate with these essential blood proteins where the binding constant, K , and the degree of cooperativity of particle²protein binding (Hill constant, n), depends on particle size and the native protein structure. Further, is also found tentative evidence that the model proteins undergo conformational change upon association with the NPs and that the thickness of the adsorbed protein layer (bare NP diameter <50 nm) progressively increases with NP size. These effects have potential general importance for understanding NP aggregation in biological media and the interaction of NP with biological materials broadly.

While studying the protein adsorption, blood cell aggregation, and C3 adsorption onto AuNPs to evaluate their complement activation potential and blood compatibility, it has been observed that these nanoparticles do not induce any complement activation or blood cell aggregation [41]. It has also been reported that particles were non-hemolytic, and the adsorptions of proteins were

negligible, further validating its significance in drug delivery and gene delivery applications.

An attempt has been made to evaluate the protein adsorption, blood compatibility and complement activation potential of two batches of Swarna bhasma preparation, along with its physicochemical characterization [42]. Red blood cell hemolysis, aggregation studies with blood cells, protein adsorption, complement C3 adsorption, platelet activation and tight junction permeability in the Caco-2 cell line were investigated. It was reported that the Swarna bhasma preparations with a crystallite size of 28-35 nm did not induce any blood cell aggregation or protein adsorption. The activation potential of these preparations towards the complement system or platelets was negligible. These particles were also non-cytotoxic. Swarna bhasma particles opened the tight junctions in Caco-2 cell experiments. The results suggest the application of Swarna bhasma preparations as a therapeutic agent in clinical medicine from a biological safety point of view.

He et al. [43] investigated the possible effects of polyethylene glycol-coated AuNPs (PEG@AuNPs) and citric acid-coated AuNPs (CT-AuNPs) on the blood cell function and distribution of those nanoparticles in blood components including erythrocytes, leukocytes, platelets (PLTs) cells and plasma. It was found that the amount of CT-AuNPs engulfed by leukocytes was four folds more compared to PEG@AuNPs, indicating that PEGylation might have the ability to escape the immune system. It is also reported that each leukocyte uptake more AuNPs particles than individual platelet.

Ma et al. [44] described a universal bio-conjugation approach that uses a new recombinant fusion protein combining two distinct domains. These researchers have identified and characterized the remarkable ability to bind gold nanoparticles (GNPs) by forming

gold–sulfur bonds (Au–S). The C-terminal part of this multi-domain construct is the SpyCatcher from *Streptococcus pyogenes*, which provides the ability to capture recombinant proteins encoding a SpyTag. It was shown that SpyCatcher could be immobilized covalently on GNPs through GST without losing its full functionality. It was also demonstrated that GST-SpyCatcher activated particles can covalently bind a SpyTag modified protein by simple mixing through the spontaneous formation of an unusual isopeptide bond.

Once nanoparticles enter the bloodstream, they become in contact with the different components of the blood and can potentially interfere with normal platelet function leading to bleeding or thrombosis [45]. As metallic NPs have already been used for diagnosis and treatment due to their unique characteristics, the potential interactions between metallic NPs and platelets have not been widely studied and reported. This review article focuses on the factors that can affect platelet activation and aggregation by metal NPs and the nature of such interactions, providing a summary of the effect of various metal NPs on platelet function available in the literature [45].

A first-time investigation on the effects of polymeric, metallic and nonmetallic nanoparticles on red blood cells' hemocompatibility was done by Mehrizi [46]. The authors reviewed the reported impacts of polymeric, metallic and carbon-based nanoparticles on Red Blood Cells (RBCs). Their study results have shown that using negatively charged dendrimers, unsaturated/uncharged liposomes, and PEGylated forms of NPs and RBCs are the best approaches to improve the hemocompatibility conditions of red blood cells. However, large cationic dendrimers, liposomes composed of saturated lipid with long acyl chains, and cationic chitosan nanoparticles have less RBC compatibility. In addition, polymeric nanoparticles have more surface modification capacity, making it possible to make more hemocompatible derivatives. Among metallic nanoparticles, gold and iron nanoparticles were more RBC compatible. However, the smaller size, higher concentration and longer exposure time of these nanoparticles can induce hemolysis and morphological changes in RBCs. On the other side, nonmetallic nanoparticles mostly had poor RBC compatibility, but their effects on RBCs strongly depended on their concentration and physicochemical properties and could be controllable. As a result, the use of polyethylene glycol (PEG), gold, polymeric, and iron nanoparticles in the design of protocols to maintain the survival, structure and activity of red blood cells for improving hemocompatibility can be more effective.

Is it possible to alter nanoparticles from the toxic nature to make non-toxic nature?

Since nanoparticles have a wide range of applications in biomedicine and as drug delivery carriers, developing biocompatible and non-toxic nanomaterials is critical. Understanding the mechanism of nanoparticle toxicity will help researchers create nanoparticles that are less harmful to the environment. The redesign techniques must be chosen based on the principal mechanism of toxicity, as well as what changes to the nanomaterial can be made without affecting its ability to perform in its intended use. Nanomaterials can be constructed to have a negative surface charge, employ ligands like polyethylene glycol to inhibit protein binding, or have a shape that discourages binding with a cell surface to limit interactions with the cell surface. The toxic species can be replaced by less harmful components with similar characteristics to reduce nanoparticle dissolution to toxic ions. The nanoparticle can be capped with shell material, and the nanoparticle's morphology can be chosen to reduce surface area and therefore disintegration.

In addition, a chelating agent can be co-introduced or functionalized into the nanomaterials' surface. The band gap of the material can be modified either by utilizing various elements or by doping, a shell layer can be added to prevent direct contact with the core, or antioxidant molecules can be attached to the nanoparticle surface to limit the generation of reactive oxygen species. It's critical to examine whether a redesign method minimizes toxicity to species in relevant environmental compartments while redesigning nanoparticles. It's also important to make sure the nanomaterial retains the crucial physicochemical features that led to its inclusion in a product or device.

Conclusion

Undoubtedly, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are by far the most studied nanomaterials, primarily due to their immense potential in biomedical applications. As a consequence, it is obvious that huge demands surfaced to evaluate the health impact of these materials. Certain aspects could force us to believe the toxicity threat of AuNPs.

For instance, small-sized AuNPs may have been associated with toxicity, due to fact that their high surface area relative to their volume. This leads to enlarged absorption capacity and may increase the chance of interacting with biomolecules, effectively [47]. Secondly, AuNPs are believed to be the least toxic, and thus the most appropriate for biological/medical applications. However, due to their low rate of clearance from circulation streams and tissues, they may lead to health problems [48]. Further, the toxicological behavior of gold nanoparticles can be influenced by the physicochemical properties, including size, shape, surface charge, and other factors, such as methods used in the synthesis of gold nanoparticles, models used, dose, *in vivo* route of administration, and interference of gold nanoparticles with *in vitro* toxicity assay systems.

Most engineered nanoparticles are far less toxic than household cleaning products, insecticides used on family pets, and over-the-counter dandruff remedies. Certainly, the nanoparticles used as drug carriers for chemotherapeutics are much less toxic than the drugs they carry and are designed to carry drugs safely to tumors without harming organs and healthy tissue. Most importantly, this review points towards the toxicological aspect of AuNPs, albeit a few studies are denying that important fact. For time being, it may be reasonable to conclude here that more *in vivo* studies are necessary to precisely examine the effects of nanoplastics in human physiology, together with accurate quantification of environmental nanoparticle loads and a more standardized methodology to address the confounding variability of *in vitro* approaches.

Future Scope

There is a great scope for this ever-increasing research. To elaborate, the toxicity and biodistribution profile of differently sized AuNPs still remains controversial and incomplete, thus hindering their further applications. But, the positive ray of hope is that several results of the biodistribution show that AuNPs with larger sizes, approximately 42.5 and 61.2 nm, accumulated mainly in liver and spleen while little or none were found in heart, kidney and lung.

On the other hand, smaller ones, approximately 6.2 and 24.3 nm, are distributed not only in liver and spleen but also in other organs. Additionally, most of the AuNPs were excreted out in less than 30 days, whereas there were still bits of remains in liver and spleen up to 90 days, especially for the 42.5 and 61.2 nm Au NPs. These findings are meaningful for the design of the AuNPs in the biomedical fields in the ensuing days.

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